

Study of Equilibrium Constants of Cu^{2+} -Malonic Acid Complexes at Various Ionic Strengths and in Dioxane Water Mixtures

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The interactions of Cu^{2+} -malonic acid in aqueous and 20, 40, 60, 80% (v/v) dioxane-water mixtures have been investigated potentiometrically at 0.032, 0.052, 0.072, 0.092 and 0.112 *M* ionic strength. It is observed that Cu^{2+} forms 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with the ligand in all the solvent mixtures.

The distance of closest approach 'a' between the metal ion and the ligand calculated was found to be 4Å. The probable complexation equilibria have been examined from the variation of $\log K_1$ with ionic strength of the medium. The two types of 1:1 complexes occurring by the reactions:

are proposed. The effect of dielectric constant on the $pK/\log K$ values is also discussed.

COPPER complexes of malonic acid are studied by the workers¹⁻³. The substituent effect on the stabilities of the complexes formed between Cu^{2+} with mono and di substituted malonic acid has been thoroughly discussed by Sammartano and coworkers⁴. In our earlier studies, we reported the uranyl complexes with malonic acid^{5,6}. The purpose of the study reported here was to obtain more precise information about the behaviour of this ligand in solution and stability constants of the complexes. In particular, it was tried, (i) to confirm the exact complexation equilibria of the complexes, (ii) to calculate the interionic distance between the ligand and the metal ion and (iii) to study the effect of dielectric constant on the stabilities.

Experimental

The chemicals used were AnalaR grade. Malonic acid obtained from Fluka (Germany) was purified by repeated crystallization. The concentration of the copper ion was estimated by the standard procedure⁷. All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water. 1-4 Dioxane of B.D.H. was purified by the standard procedure⁸. Freshly distilled dioxane was always used in the titrations and its purity was checked by potassium iodide. The details of other chemicals, measurement of pH are given in earlier papers^{9,10}.

The ionic strength of the solution was maintained by the addition of appropriate amounts of 1*M* sodium perchlorate solution. The calibration of glass electrode in different solvent mixtures and conversion of B value (pH meter reading) into hydrogen ion concentration was done by the method of Van Uitert *et al*^{11,12}.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were evaluated by the method of Irving and Rossotti^{13,14}. The accurate values of pK were calculated by pointwise calculations and presented in Table 1. $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were obtained by pointwise calculations. Their accurate values were calculated by the method of least-squares (Table 2). The maximum value of $\bar{n}$ at each ionic strength was around 1.9. The formation of 1:2 complex was proved by the standard procedure¹⁵. The standard deviation of these values was between 0.01 and 0.05. A representative data i.e., Cu^{2+} -malonic acid in 60% dioxane-water mixture explain adequately the precision of the experimental work (Table 3).

It is seen (Table 2) that at each percentage of dioxane, the values of $\log K_1$ decrease and $\log K_2$ increase with the increase in ionic strength. The

TABLE 1— pK VALUES OF MALONIC ACID IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS
Temp = 30°

μ	pK_1/pK_2	Dioxane-percentage (v/v)				
		0	20	40	60	80
0.032	pK_1	5.59	6.37	7.38	8.28	10.07
	pK_2	2.83	3.29	3.93	4.85	7.05
0.052	pK_1	5.50	6.25	7.22	8.21	10.04
	pK_2	2.80	3.23	3.88	4.82	6.98
0.072	pK_1	5.47	6.22	7.19	8.16	9.99
	pK_2	2.73	3.18	3.85	4.80	6.96
0.092	pK_1	5.40	6.12	6.97	8.10	9.90
	pK_2	2.70	3.14	3.80	4.77	6.76
0.112	pK_1	5.30	6.08	6.79	8.05	9.87
	pK_2	2.68	3.10	3.74	4.74	6.69

* For correspondence.

TABLE 2—Log K VALUES OF Cu^{2+} -MALONIC ACID COMPLEXES IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS

		Temp=30°				
		Dioxane-percentage (v/v)				
μ	$\log K_1/\log K_2$	0	20	40	60	80
0.032	$\log K_1$	5.50	6.40	8.12	10.15	14.04
	$\log K_2$	2.85	3.86	4.91	5.66	10.86
0.052	$\log K_1$	5.38	6.27	7.96	9.92	14.34
	$\log K_2$	3.05	3.97	5.05	5.91	11.42
0.072	$\log K_1$	5.30	6.18	7.80	9.74	13.72
	$\log K_2$	3.10	4.08	5.12	6.34	11.69
0.092	$\log K_1$	5.20	6.12	7.66	9.48	13.54
	$\log K_2$	3.27	4.20	5.22	6.50	—
0.112	$\log K_1$	5.10	6.07	7.41	9.33	13.34
	$\log K_2$	3.37	4.31	5.31	6.68	—

 TABLE 3—CALCULATIONS OF STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Cu^{2+} -MALONIC ACID. MEDIUM . 60% (v/v) DIOXANE-WATER

		Temp. 30°			$\mu=0.032M(\text{NaClO}_4)$	
B	$\bar{n}_{\text{expt}}$	$\bar{n}_{\text{calcd}}$	pL	$\Delta\bar{n}$		
2.8	0.379	0.377	11.029	0.002		
3.0	0.565	0.537	10.645	-0.022		
3.2	0.583	0.581	9.251	0.002		
3.4	0.606	0.618	8.859	-0.012		
3.6	0.637	0.635	8.471	0.002		
3.8	0.679	0.674	8.087	0.005		
4.0	0.727	0.730	7.712	-0.003		
4.2	0.805	0.819	7.349	-0.014		
5.0	1.341	1.348	6.084	-0.007		
5.2	1.482	1.480	5.825	0.002		
5.4	1.598	1.586	5.581	0.012		
5.6	1.623	1.630	5.346	-0.007		
Slope = 6.653×10^{15}		$\log K_{ML_1} = 10.158$				
Intercept = 1.435×10^{10}		$\log K_{ML_2} = 5.666$				
Standard deviation = 0.011.						

magnitude of the increment is, however, not the same for all dioxane-water mixtures. The Bronsted equation¹⁶

$$\log K = \log K^0 + A\Delta Z^2$$

and

$$pK = pK^0 - A\Delta Z^2$$

were used to determine the magnitude of ΔZ^2 in dioxane-water mixtures, where,

$$\Delta Z^2 = Z^2_{\text{product}} - Z^2_{\text{reactants}}$$

The values of A and B were taken from the work of Harned and Owen¹⁷.

The plots of pK/log K against $\sqrt{\mu}$: The plots of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ were linear. The magnitude of ΔZ^2 observed for each plot in all dioxane-water mixtures are given in Table 4.

 TABLE 4—VALUES OF ΔZ^2 OBTAINED FROM THE SLOPES

Reaction constant	Dioxane percentage (v/v)				Expected value on the basis of complex equilibria
	0	20	40	60	
pK_1	2.24	1.72	1.09	0.24	2
pK_2	3.37	2.70	2.94	0.61	4
$\log K_1$	4.48	2.89	2.23	2.16	-4
$\log K_2$	5.69	3.17	2.06	2.77	4

The observed ΔZ^2 are less than the expected values. The discrepancy between the two is significant at higher percentage of dioxane, due to the use of a simplified form of Bronsted equation.

Scatchard has modified the Debye-Hückel equation by introducing a factor for the size of the ions. Using this modification in Bronsted-Christiansen equation¹⁸, one gets

$$\log K = \log K^0 + \frac{A\Delta Z^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + B.a \sqrt{\mu}}$$

where A and B are Debye-Hückel constants and 'a' is the ion size parameter of the chelate. The value of 'a' was computed only for aqueous medium by putting different values of 'a' in the above equation and observing the influence on $\log K$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$. According to the equation $\log K$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ should be linear and parallel to the $\sqrt{\mu}$ axis. All the plots (except for $a=4\text{\AA}$) are not parallel to the $\sqrt{\mu}$ axis. It is, therefore, concluded that the interionic distance between the metal ion and the ligand is $4\text{\AA}$. This is further confirmed from the plot of $\log K$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}/1 + B.a \sqrt{\mu} = \sqrt{\mu}/1 + 1.3204u \sqrt{\mu}$ which gave slope value 2.89.

The closest distance of approach between the metal ion and the ligand is thoroughly discussed in our previous work⁶. In aqueous solution, total size of the hydrated copper ion is $3.93\text{\AA}$ and magnitude of Δ would be $1.43\text{\AA}$.

Nature of complexation equilibria: The pK_1 value of malonic acid in water is 2.68 and metal-ligand formation number in this region is around 0.5, since in this pH range the ligand is partly dissociated. The interaction of Cu^{2+} with both the species i.e., H_2L and HL^- is possible. The 1:1 complexation may, therefore, take place by the following equilibria: (a) $\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{L} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuHL}^+ + \text{H}^+$; (b) $\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{HL}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{CuL} + \text{H}^+$.

The magnitude of ΔZ^2 for the reactions a and b are -2 and -4 respectively. The calculated value from the ionic parameters is -2.89 which is intermediate between the two. It is, therefore, expected that 1:1 complexation is occurring simultaneously by both the equilibria. The complexation reactions a and b would proceed at 0, 20, 40, 60%, while a would be mostly favoured at 80%, in agreement with the earlier work.

Effect of dielectric constant on stabilities: In the present investigation, the equilibrium constants $pK/\log K$ increase with decrease in dielectric constants. The plot of $pK/\log K$ against $1/D$ were non-linear while those against mole fraction exhibit linearity.

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